

INTEGRATION OF LLVM AND ICARUS VERILOG FOR THE COMPILATION AND SIMULATION OF CUSTOM PROCESSORS

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ABSTRACT: This paper presents a methodology for the integration of LLVM and Icarus Verilog, aiming at the compilation and simulation of custom processors. The combination of these two technologies provides an efficient workflow, from hardware description to executable code generation. The research involved extensive research and practical steps to enable LLVM to recognize the Cpu0 educational processor as a valid target, including cloning and building LLVM with specific Cpu0 support. The work details the process of generating assembly code for the Cpu0 architecture from a C++ program and converting it to a hexadecimal format readable by Verilog. Furthermore, the study explored the adaptation of the Cpu0 architecture by demonstrating how to successfully remove a register and an instruction, showcasing the flexibility of the LLVM backend. This methodology provides a practical and accessible approach for developers and researchers, filling the gap of didactic sources on the subject. The results highlight the potential for this integration to streamline the workflow for developing application-specific processors.

Keywords: Compilation; LLVM; Simulation; Processors; Verilog.

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of processor architectures has been one of the main drivers of technological progress in recent decades. As the complexity of computational systems

increases, it becomes essential to have efficient tools for the compilation and simulation of custom processors. In this context, the use of LLVM (Low-Level Virtual Machine) and Icarus Verilog can offer an effective approach for the development and verification of new processors.

LLVM is a compilation toolset that provides a robust infrastructure for code optimization and generation. Its modular architecture allows easy integration with various programming languages and hardware platforms (Project 2024). On the other hand, Icarus Verilog is an open-source implementation of the Verilog compiler, widely used for modeling and simulating digital circuits (Williams 2019). The combination of these two technologies can provide an efficient workflow, from hardware description to executable code generation.

This article presents a methodology for the integration of LLVM and Icarus Verilog, aiming at the compilation and simulation of custom processors. Although the integration of LLVM and Icarus Verilog was not directly addressed in the classes, we identified the need to explore this combination of tools due to the scarcity of didactic sources on the subject. Additionally, we propose a detailed tutorial on how to perform this integration, with the aim of providing a practical and accessible approach for developers and researchers who wish to explore this combination of tools.

2. METHODOLOGY

During the development of this work, we conducted extensive research to enable LLVM to recognize Cpu0 as a valid target. Below are some of the main resources we used:

2.1 Official LLVM documentation

The official LLVM documentation was a crucial source of information on how to add new targets and modify LLVM's backend. LLVM Documentation. (Project 2024)

2.2 Source code artisan: setting up a new backend

During our research, we used the Source Code Artisan guide on configuring a new LLVM backend. This guide provided valuable insights into setting up a new target triple, configuring the driver, and creating a new target. The step-by-step instructions helped us understand the process of developing an LLVM backend, which was crucial for our project (Artisan 2020).

However, we encountered an issue with the ``cmake/modules/LLVM-BUILD.cmake`` file during the build process, indicating a configuration problem in the build system. Despite

following the guide's instructions, the issue persisted, requiring us to delve deeper into the CMake configuration and make necessary adjustments to resolve the problem.

2.3 Github repositories

We also utilized several GitHub repositories that provided tutorials and practical examples for creating an LLVM backend. However, the issue with the ``cmake/modules/LLVM-BUILD.cmake`` file persisted. Below are some of the main repositories we used:

The repository by Jonathan2251 on GitHub offers a step-by-step tutorial for creating a new LLVM backend from scratch. Written in reStructuredText and built using the Sphinx Python Documentation Generator, the repository includes detailed instructions on setting up a new target, creating a driver, and integrating with LLVM (Jonathan2251, 2024).

The repository by P2Tree on GitHub provides a tutorial to learn LLVM, focusing on creating a backend to compile machine code for Cpu0, a simple RISC processor. It includes detailed instructions for setting up a new target, creating a driver, and integrating with LLVM (P2Tree, 2024).

3. MATERIALS

3.1 Related Work

Several studies have explored the integration of software and hardware tools for the development of custom processors. Nery (2020) presented a detailed study on the development of a base tool for creating application-specific processors. The aim of this work was to study the LLVM framework, with an emphasis on the process of developing a backend for this framework for a new computational architecture, using the didactic microprocessor Cpu0 as a reference. Additionally, modifications were made to the compiler to reflect possible changes (Nery, 2020).

Our work differs by proposing an integrated methodology that combines the capabilities of LLVM and Verilog for the compilation and simulation of custom processors. This approach aims to fill the gaps identified in previous studies, providing a practical and accessible solution for developers and researchers.

3.2 Theoretical Foundation

3.2.1 LLVM (Low-Level Virtual Machine)

LLVM is a collection of compilation tools that provides a solid infrastructure for code optimization and generation. Initially developed by the University of Illinois, LLVM was designed to be modular and reusable, facilitating integration with various programming languages and hardware platforms. LLVM consists of three main components: the front-end, the middle-end, and the back-end. The front-end translates the source code into an intermediate representation (IR), the middle-end performs optimizations on this representation, and the back-end generates machine code specific to the target architecture (Project, 2021).

3.2.2 Icarus Verilog

Icarus Verilog is an open-source implementation of the Verilog compiler, which allows the simulation and synthesis of designs written in Verilog. Developed to be a lightweight and efficient tool, Icarus Verilog is widely used for the verification and validation of hardware projects. It supports the description of digital systems at different levels of abstraction, from logic gates to complex behaviors. The tool is especially useful for simulating circuits before physical implementation, facilitating error detection and design optimization (Williams 2019).

3.2.3 Integration of LLVM and Icarus Verilog

The combination of LLVM and Icarus Verilog can provide an efficient workflow for the development of custom processors. LLVM can be used for code compilation and optimization, while Icarus Verilog allows hardware modeling and simulation. This integration enables developers and researchers to explore new processor architectures more efficiently, from hardware description to executable code generation. The methodology proposed in this work aims to facilitate this integration by providing a detailed tutorial on how to use these tools together.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Building LLVM with Cpu0 Support

The initial goal of the project was to compile a customized version of LLVM with support for the Cpu0 target, using the *lbd* repository (Jonathan2251, 2024), integrated with version 12.x of LLVM. This section details the steps taken to achieve this objective.

4.1.1 Cloning Repositories and Initial Configuration

To start the project, the LLVM and *lbd* repositories (Jonathan2251, 2024) were cloned,

and the directories were organized to integrate the Cpu0 files into LLVM's codebase following the commands in Figure 1. The LLVM repository was synchronized with a specific version to ensure compatibility with the Cpu0 target.

Figure 1 – Code cloning and Directory Organization.

```
git clone https://github.com/Jonathan2251/lbd.git
mkdir llvm
cd llvm
mkdir test
git clone https://github.com/llvm/llvm-project.git
cd llvm-project
git checkout -b 12.x origin/release/12.x
git checkout e8a397203c67adbeae04763ce25c6a5ae76af52c
```

Source: The authors.

4.1.2 Integrating the Cpu0 Target into LLVM

The integration of the Cpu0 target into LLVM was carried out in two main steps. First, symbolic links for relevant directories were created within the LLVM project, using the *ln* command, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2 – Creating of symbolic links.

```
ln -s ../llvm-project/clang clang
ln -s ../llvm-project/llvm llvm
```

Source: The authors.

In the next step, the specific files for the Cpu0 target were copied into the directories within the LLVM codebase using the code in Figure 3.

Figure 3 – Creating of symbolic links.

```
cp -rf /lbd/lbdex/llvm/modify/llvm/* $/llvm/test/llvm/.
cp -rf Cpu0 $~/llvm/test/llvm/lib/Target/.
cp -rf /lbd/lbdex/regression-test/Cpu0 $/llvm/test/llvm/test/CodeGen/.
```

Source: The authors.

4.1.3 LLVM build process

The LLVM *build* process was conducted in a separate directory to organize the files generated during configuration and compilation. Initial configuration was done using *cmake* with specific parameters to enable the Cpu0 target and optimize *tableGen* generation. The compilation was completed with the *make* command present in the Figure 4:

Figure 4 – LLVM build.

```
mkdir build
cd build
cmake -DCMAKE_BUILD_TYPE=Debug -DCMAKE_CXX_COMPILER=
clang++ -DCMAKE_C_COMPILER=clang -
  LLVM_TARGETS_TO_BUILD=Cpu0 -DLLVM_ENABLE_PROJECTS="
clang" -DLLVM_OPTIMIZED_TABLEGEN=On -
  LLVM_PARALLEL_COMPILE_JOBS=4 -
  LLVM_PARALLEL_LINK_JOBS=1 -G "Unix_Makefiles" -
  LLVM_USE_LINKER=lld ../llvm
time make
```

Source: The authors.

These steps resulted in a version of LLVM that supports the Cpu0 target. It is possible to verify if the process was completed correctly by listing the targets and checking if Cpu0 is among them with the command in Figure 5.

Figure 5 – Checking supported targets.

```
cd ~/llvm/test/build/bin
./llc --version
```

Source: The authors.

4.2 Generation of Assembly Code for the Cpu0 Architecture

To test the integration between LLVM and the Cpu0 architecture, simply follow a sequence of steps to generate the assembly code from a C++ program (in this case, named *main_run.cpp*). Below are the detailed steps carried out in the *~/lbd/lbdex/input* directory.

4.2.1 Generation of Bytecode

Initially, the program *main_run.cpp* was compiled by specifying clang for the MIPS target, generating a file bytecode after use of the code in Figure 6.

Figure 6 – Generation of bytecode.

```
~/llvm/test/build/bin/clang -target mips-unknown-linux-
gnu -c main_run.cpp -emit-llvm -o main_run.bc
```

Source: The authors.

4.2.2 Generation of the Binary Object for Cpu0

After generating the bytecode, the resulting file *main_run.bc* is converted to *main_run.cpu0.o* using the parameters *-march=cpu0*, which instructs llc to use the Cpu0 backend for generating the object file, and *-relocation-model=pic*, which specifies the chosen

simulations to record and analyze the processor's internal signals. To do this, we made a series of changes to the *Cpu0.v* file, which contains the Verilog description of the architecture, and used some commands along with *GTKWave*.

Initially, we added the following lines to the "main" module in the *Cpu0.v*. The first line, in Figure 10, added will generate a *.vcd* file containing some of the circuit components to be examined during test execution. The second line, in turn, indicates which scope will be analyzed.

Figure 10 – Modifications to the main in the *Cpu0.v* file.

```
$dumpfile("test.vcd");  
$dumpvars(0, main);
```

Source: The authors.

Next, to generate the *.vvp* file that will perform the test of the *cpu0.v* file containing the *Cpu0* circuits, simply execute the command "iverilog -o *test.vvp* *cpu0.v*". Finally, to execute the test, use the command "vvp *test.vvp*". At the end of the test, the *teste.vcd* file will be generated, which can be opened with *GTKWave* to examine the signals present in the circuit.

4.4 Modifying the *Cpu0* Architecture

As part of the experiment, we modified the *Cpu0* architecture integrated with LLVM to explore how registers and instructions can be added, removed, or altered.

4.4.1 Removing a Register

One of the *Cpu0* registers was hidden from the architecture, changing both the register definition and its references in the modules related to code generation, assembly parsing and disassembly.

The register we removed was *v0*, generally used as a function return register. The steps begin with removing the line in Figure 11 that is his definition in the *Cpu0RegisterInfo.td* file:

Figure 11 – Removed line in *Cpu0RegisterInfo.td* file.

```
def V0: Cpu0GPRReg < 2, "2">, DwarfRegNum <[2]>;
```

Source: The authors.

Then, in the file *Cpu0CallingConv.td*, remove the references to *V0* in the following code snippet. The result can be seen in Figure 12:

Figure 12 – Excerpt in *Cpu0CallingConv.td* file after removing V0.

```
def RetCC_Cpu0EABI : CallingConv<[  
  // i32 are returned in registers V1, A0, A1  
  CCIIfType<[i32], CCAssignToReg<[V1, A0, A1]>>  

```

Source: The authors.

In the file *Cpu0Disassembler.cpp*, you need to remove "*Cpu0::V0*", resulting in Figure 13. Also, remove ".Case(*"v0"*, *Cpu0::V0*)" in the file *Cpu0AsmParser.cpp*, resulting in Figure 14.

Figure 13 – Excerpt from *Cpu0Disassembler.cpp* file after removing V0.

```
// Decoder tables for GPR register  
static const unsigned CPURegsTable[] = {  
  Cpu0::ZERO, Cpu0::AT, Cpu0::V1,  
  Cpu0::A0, Cpu0::A1, Cpu0::T9, Cpu0::T0,  
  Cpu0::T1, Cpu0::S0, Cpu0::S1, Cpu0::GP,  

```

Source: The authors.

Figure 14 – Excerpt from *Cpu0AsmParser.cpp* file after removing V0.

```
int Cpu0AsmParser::matchRegisterName(StringRef Name) {  
  
  int CC;  
  CC = StringSwitch<unsigned>(Name)  
    .Case("zero", Cpu0::ZERO)  
    .Case("at", Cpu0::AT)  
    .Case("v0", Cpu0::V0)  
    .Case("v1", Cpu0::V1)  
    .Case("a0", Cpu0::A0)  
    .Case("a1", Cpu0::A1)  
    .Case("t9", Cpu0::T9)  
    .Case("t0", Cpu0::T0)  
    .Case("t1", Cpu0::T1)  
    .Case("s0", Cpu0::S0)  
    .Case("s1", Cpu0::S1)  
    .Case("sw", Cpu0::SW)  
    .Case("gp", Cpu0::GP)  
    .Case("fp", Cpu0::FP)  
    .Case("sp", Cpu0::SP)  
    .Case("lr", Cpu0::LR)  
    .Case("pc", Cpu0::PC)  
    .Case("hi", Cpu0::HI)  
    .Case("lo", Cpu0::LO)  
    .Case("epc", Cpu0::EPC)  
    .Default(-1);  
  
  if (CC != -1)  
    return CC;  
  
  return -1;  
}
```

Source: The authors.

Finally, simply remove references to V0 in a file sequence, some references existed only to V0, so for security reasons, references only to V0 were replaced by V1 (and V1 by t9 where necessary) in the following files: *Cpu0LongBranch.cpp* (Figure 15), *Cpu0ISelLowering.cpp* (Figure 16 and Figure 17) and *Cpu0SEFrameLowering.cpp* (Figure 18).

Figure 15 – Excerpt from Cpu0LongBranch.cpp file after removing V0.

```
static void emitGPDisp(MachineFunction &F, const
    Cpu0InstrInfo *TII) {
    MachineBasicBlock &MBB = F.front();
    MachineBasicBlock::iterator I = MBB.begin();
    DebugLoc DL = MBB.findDebugLoc(MBB.begin());
    BuildMI(MBB, I, DL, TII->get(Cpu0::LUI), Cpu0::V1)
        .addExternalSymbol("_gp_disp", Cpu0II::MO_ABS_HI);
    BuildMI(MBB, I, DL, TII->get(Cpu0::ADDiu), Cpu0::V1)
        .addReg(Cpu0::V1).addExternalSymbol("_gp_disp",
            Cpu0II::MO_ABS_LO);
    MBB.removeLiveIn(V1);
}
```

Source: The authors.

Figure 16 – Excerpt from Cpu0ISelLowering.cpp file after removing V0 in AddrReg.

```
// Store stack offset in V1, store jump target in V0.
// Glue CopyToReg and
// EH_RETURN nodes, so that instructions are emitted
// back-to-back.
unsigned OffsetReg = Cpu0::t9;
unsigned AddrReg = Cpu0::V1;
Chain = DAG.getCopyToReg(Chain, DL, OffsetReg, Offset,
    SDValue());
Chain = DAG.getCopyToReg(Chain, DL, AddrReg, Handler,
    Chain.getValue(1));
return DAG.getNode(Cpu0ISD::EH_RETURN, DL, MVT::Other,
    Chain,
        DAG.getRegister(OffsetReg, Ty),
        DAG.getRegister(AddrReg,
            getPointerTy(MF.getDataLayout())),
        Chain.getValue(1));
}
```

Source: The authors.

Figure 17 – Excerpt from file Cpu0ISelLowering.cpp after removing V0 from the rest of the references.


```
if (MF.getFunction().hasStructRetAttr()) {
    Cpu0FunctionInfo *Cpu0FI = MF.getInfo<
        Cpu0FunctionInfo>();
    unsigned Reg = Cpu0FI->getSRetReturnReg();

    if (!Reg)
        llvm_unreachable("sret_virtual_register_not_
            created_in_the_entry_block");
    SDValue Val =
        DAG.getCopyFromReg(Chain, DL, Reg, getPointerTy(
            DAG.getDataLayout()));
    unsigned V1 = Cpu0::V1;

    Chain = DAG.getCopyToReg(Chain, DL, V1, Val, Flag);
    Flag = Chain.getValue(1);
    RetOps.push_back(DAG.getRegister(V1, getPointerTy(
        DAG.getDataLayout())));
}
```

Source: The authors.

Figure 18 – Excerpt from Cpu0 Frame Lowering.cpp file after removing V0.

```
if (Cpu0FI->callsEhDwarf()) {
    BuildMI(MBB, MBB, dl, TII.get(ADDu), Cpu0::V1).
        addReg(FP).addReg(ZERO)
        .setMIFlag(MachineInstr::FrameSetup);
}
```

Source: The authors.

4.4.2 Removing an instruction

One of the instructions in the Cpu0 architecture was hidden, making it "invisible" to LLVM. This was done by modifying the files responsible for describing the instruction set in the Cpu0 backend. Initially, we simply omitted the definition of the instruction in the *Cpu0InstrInfo.td* file, which is located in Figure 19.

:

Figure 19 – Removing the instruction definition in the Cpu0InstrInfo.td file.

```
def MUL: ArithLogicR<0x17, "mul", mul, IIImul, CPURegs,
    1>;
```

Source: The authors.

However, this modification alone results in an error, see in Figure 20, indicating that LLVM could not find a valid implementation for the removed instruction during the instruction selection stage.

Figure 20 – Error when omitting instruction from the backend.

```
LLVM ERROR: Cannot select: t18: i32 = mul nsw 16,  
Constant: i32<3>
```

Source: The authors.

Thus, to resolve the error and complete the instruction removal, the *setOperationAction* command was used in the *Cpu0ISelLowering.cpp* file, specifically within the constructor of the *Cpu0TargetLowering* class. This function allows defining how the compiler should handle certain operations for a target architecture, which is useful for modifying the default behavior of the compiler for specific operations. In Figure 21, commands are added to expand the MUL instruction.

Figure 21 – Adding commands to expand the MUL instruction into a sequence of equivalent instructions.

```
setOperationAction(ISD::MUL, MVT::i32, Expand);  
setOperationAction(ISD::MULHS, MVT::i32, Expand);  
setOperationAction(ISD::MULHU, MVT::i32, Expand);
```

Source: The authors.

With this, to observe the impacts of removing the MUL instruction, we tested a piece of code, Figure 22, and analyzed the generated hexadecimal code before, Figure 23, and after, Figure 24, the modifications.

Figure 22 – Function used to test the impacts of removing an instruction on the final generation of the hexadecimal code.

```
int main() {  
    int a = 1;  
    int b = 2;  
    a = a * b;  
    b = b * 3;  
    return 0;  
}
```

Source: The authors.

Figure 23 – Hexadecimal code generated before the removal of the MUL instruction.


```

/*0: */      09 dd ff f0      /*addiu $sp, $sp, -16 */
/*4: */      02 cd 00 0c      /*st   $fp, 12($sp)*/
/*8: */      11 cd 00 00      /*move $fp, $sp*/
/*c: */      09 20 00 00      /*addiu $2, $zero, 0*/
/*10: */     02 2c 00 08      /*st   $2, 8($fp)*/
/*14: */     09 30 00 01      /*addiu $3, $zero, 1*/
/*18: */     02 3c 00 04      /*st   $3, 4($fp)*/
/*1c: */     09 30 00 02      /*addiu $3, $zero, 2*/
/*20: */     02 3c 00 00      /*st   $3, 0($fp)*/
/*24: */     01 3c 00 04      /*ld   $3, 4($fp)*/
/*28: */     01 4c 00 00      /*ld   $4, 0($fp)*/
/*2c: */     17 33 40 00      /*mul  $3, $3, $4*/
/*30: */     02 3c 00 04      /*st   $3, 4($fp)*/
/*34: */     01 3c 00 00      /*ld   $3, 0($fp)*/
/*38: */     09 40 00 03      /*addiu $4, $zero, 3*/
/*3c: */     17 33 40 00      /*mul  $3, $3, $4*/
/*40: */     02 3c 00 00      /*st   $3, 0($fp)*/
/*44: */     11 dc 00 00      /*move $sp, $fp*/
/*48: */     01 cd 00 0c      /*ld   $fp, 12($sp)*/
/*4c: */     09 dd 00 10      /*addiu $sp, $sp, 16*/
/*50: */     3c e0 00 00      /*ret  $lr*/
/*54: */     00 00 00 00      /*nop*/

```

Source: The authors.

Figure 24 – Hexadecimal code generated after the removal of the MUL instruction.

```

/* 0: */      09 dd ff f0      /*addiu $sp, $sp, -16*/
/* 4: */      02 cd 00 0c      /*st   $fp, 12($sp)*/
/* 8: */      11 cd 00 00      /*move $fp, $sp*/
/* c: */      09 20 00 00      /*addiu $2, $zero, 0*/
/* 10: */     02 2c 00 08      /*st   $2, 8($fp)*/
/* 14: */     09 30 00 01      /*addiu $3, $zero, 1*/
/* 18: */     02 3c 00 04      /*st   $3, 4($fp)*/
/* 1c: */     09 30 00 02      /*addiu $3, $zero, 2*/
/* 20: */     02 3c 00 00      /*st   $3, 0($fp)*/
/* 24: */     01 3c 00 04      /*ld   $3, 4($fp)*/
/* 28: */     01 4c 00 00      /*ld   $4, 0($fp)*/
/* 2c: */     41 34 00 00      /*mult $3, $4*/
/* 30: */     47 30 00 00      /*mflo $3*/
/* 34: */     46 40 00 00      /*mfhi $4*/
/* 38: */     02 3c 00 04      /*st   $3, 4($fp)*/
/* 3c: */     01 3c 00 00      /*ld   $3, 0($fp)*/
/* 40: */     09 40 00 03      /*addiu $4, $zero, 3*/
/* 44: */     41 34 00 00      /*mult $3, $4*/
/* 48: */     47 30 00 00      /*mflo $3*/
/* 4c: */     46 40 00 00      /*mfhi $4*/
/* 50: */     02 3c 00 00      /*st   $3, 0($fp)*/
/* 54: */     11 dc 00 00      /*move $sp, $fp*/
/* 58: */     01 cd 00 0c      /*ld   $fp, 12($sp)*/
/* 5c: */     09 dd 00 10      /*addiu $sp, $sp, 16*/
/* 60: */     3c e0 00 00      /*ret  $lr*/
/* 64: */     00 00 00 00      /*nop*/

```

Source: The authors.

5. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The objective of the project piqued the interest of the students involved, driven by their curiosity to see the theory presented in class in practice. Initially, the objective was to compile C code for the 16-bit processor developed by one of the team members. However, as this was a final project for the course on compilers and high-performance architecture. Therefore, the

target machine was upgraded to an educational processor to focus more on understanding LLVM.

To compile simple C code for the target machine (Cpu0) using LLVM, initial research was conducted to understand how LLVM is organized, how to compile for an architecture already present in LLVM, and, finally, how to add a new architecture to its collection. This was a rather confusing step due to LLVM's extensive documentation and complexity. During the compilation attempt for Cpu0, several compilation errors were encountered, ranging from incompatible versions of the gcc compiler to incompatible OS versions, frustrating the team. Furthermore, an initial attempt was made to compile using the Windows 10 OS, but later the Linux Ubuntu OS was used. Despite these problems, it was possible to compile a C file for the Cpu0 architecture using LLVM and simulate it with Icarus Verilog. Subsequently, changes were made to add new commands for the Cpu0 architecture and its simulation.

This entire research process was fantastic for the students, as it enabled them to combine the various areas covered during their academic training, such as computer architecture, graph algorithms, compilers, and mathematics.

This work demonstrated the feasibility and advantages of integrating LLVM with Icarus Verilog for the development and simulation of custom processors. The study provided a practical methodology for compiling code and validating processor architectures through detailed steps and examples, including the successful adaptation of the Cpu0 architecture. The results highlight the potential for this integration to streamline the workflow for researchers and developers, offering both flexibility and precision in the development of application-specific processors. Future research could expand on this foundation, exploring additional architectures and refining the process to enhance usability and efficiency.

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